

Case studies

**The impact of
environmental
degradation on cultural
rights**

MOTHER EARTH MSCA POSTDOCTORAL FELLOWSHIP

Lopes Fabris, Alice.

The impact of environmental degradation on cultural rights / Lopes Fabris, Alice — 1st ed. —
Brussels: VUB & MSCA Mother Earth Project, 2025.

Booklet developed within the framework of the Project Mother Earth (Marie Skłodowska-Curie
Actions), funded by the European Union.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18185207

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the
author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European
Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held
responsible for them.

Lopes Fabris, A. (2025). *Cases studies: the impact of environmental degradation on cultural
rights* (1st ed.). VUB & MSCA Mother Earth Project.

We would like to express our deepest gratitude to the members of the Angelim and Cañaverales communities for generously sharing their time, knowledge, and experiences. We hope that this toolkit will help to raise awareness and support their rights.

Introduction

This booklet is a part of a toolkit developed in the framework of the MSCA Project Mother Earth: The Impact of Human-Induced Environmental Degradation on the Cultural Rights of Indigenous and Afro-Indigenous Peoples.

This booklet presents case studies that illustrate how human-induced environmental degradation can impact the cultural rights and ways of life of Afro-descendant communities and Indigenous Peoples. These stories show that when land, water, and natural resources are damaged or taken over by outside actors, it is not only livelihoods that are affected (social bonds, traditions, celebrations, and intergenerational knowledge are also threatened).

The case studies highlight the connections between communities and their environment: how agriculture, local practices, music, festivals, and storytelling are intertwined with the land and water that sustain them.

The information presented, regarding the Angelim and Cañaverales community, was gathered through fieldwork with the communities themselves. Researcher visited the communities, listened to their stories through interviews. Special care was taken to understand the communities' own perspectives, experiences, and knowledge systems. The goal was to present their experiences, using clear and accessible language, while highlighting the profound impact of environmental degradation on their culture and way of life.

Environmental Degradation and Cultural Rights

This toolkit offers a framework to help readers better understand and visualise the connections between human-induced environmental degradation and its impact on the cultural rights of Afro-descendant communities and indigenous peoples. While the communities themselves may be well aware of these impacts, we are presenting this resource as a means of raising awareness among broader audiences of how environmental degradation can also harm the culture of a community. Rather, it is designed to help us understand how disruption to the natural environment poses a direct threat to the intangible heritage, community practices and ancestral knowledge that define these unique cultures.

This toolkit offers practical resources to support action and understanding. These include a section on **how to file complaints** with regional and international human rights protection mechanisms, a **caselaw guide** outlining relevant legal precedents, and a **glossary** of key terms and concepts that underpin this project.

Cases

In this section, we present two case to illustrate how environmental degradation can impact the cultural rights of traditional communities. These examples demonstrate that when land, water and natural resources are damaged, communities lose more than just their sources of food and income. They also lose their traditions, celebrations, stories and knowledge passed down through the generations.

**Angelim
communities**

**Cañaverales
community**

All photos were taken by the author and are illustrative; they do not correspond to the community.

Angelim

A community formed along a river from the descendants of former slaves. They developed a way of life centred on agriculture, mutual support and a strong connection to the land. Families worked together in the fields, helped those in need and shared responsibilities such as producing cassava flour for the region and beyond, washing clothes in the river and gathering vines from the forest. Life was simple and difficult at times, yet rich in tradition, celebration, music and dance. Elders passed down knowledge, stories and cultural practices, and the community flourished alongside the river and its natural resources.

This photo is for illustrative purposes only.

One day, a company started buying up land belonging to some community members and scaring others into leaving. They promised jobs and a better life in the city. Many people left, hoping for a better life, but it never materialised. Others were scared and fled. The company destroyed the land they acquired by planting eucalyptus trees, which damaged the soil and water sources and made traditional agriculture much more difficult.

This photo is for illustrative purposes only.

The community's daily life changed drastically. Women no longer met at the river because most people had moved far away. Cassava flour is still made, but with fewer people, and passing down knowledge has become more difficult. Local prayers and other traditional practices are held less often because there are not enough people to participate. Traditional celebrations and church gatherings that once happened every month or weekend became rare, occurring only once a year. Elders who had preserved the community's stories and knowledge either moved away or passed on, and much of the cultural memory was lost. Children, increasingly absorbed by technology, grew up without learning the community's traditions. Tales of forest spirits and other local stories stopped being told, breaking a chain of knowledge that had lasted generations.

This photo is for illustrative purposes only.

Years later, another company arrived near the river, dumping chemicals and polluting the water. Agriculture became even more difficult, and life in the community grew dangerous as fewer people remained. The first company also sprayed herbicides that contaminated fields, used drones that disrupted daily life, and carried out heavy surveillance, further restricting freedom and the connection to their land.

This photo is for illustrative purposes only.

Today, some people that left want to return to their land and resume their way of life, but their ancestral land is occupied by eucalyptus, and the soil is hard to cultivate. Despite these challenges, there is a strong willingness to rebuild the community. To do so, they need their traditional lands to be secured and resources to make a living, so that cultural practices, social ties, and knowledge can be revived and passed on to future generations.

This photo is for illustrative purposes only.

Cañaverales

In a dry region, a community was built around a manantial: a natural spring that became the heart of their life. This water source allowed them to develop a strong agricultural system in an otherwise arid area. The people of the community is known for their kindness and for creating beautiful music, which filled the town during celebrations and daily life.

This photo is for illustrative purposes only.

The manantial is deeply respected. In the early years, no one could enter it without the community's permission. Around this spring, the community grew, celebrating festivals that attracted people from across the province, building schools, and creating a lively and vibrant life. Agriculture thrived, producing enough to sustain the community and share with others. Knowledge and culture were passed on through afternoon domino gatherings, where people would socialise and teach traditions.

This photo is for illustrative purposes only.

In particular, carnival festivities are organised around the water, highlighting the manantial as the central element of cultural and social life. Music, dancing and community gatherings all revolve around this spring's water, reinforcing the deep connection between people and their environment.

This photo is for illustrative purposes only.

However, the region sits atop coal deposits, which has attracted the interest of mining companies. Mining in nearby areas had already had a severe impact on other communities, damaging water sources, agriculture and traditional ways of life. The community feared that the same fate awaited them.

This photo is for illustrative purposes only.

Mining poses a direct threat to the manantial, which is the community's source of water and life. If the water becomes polluted or runs dry, agriculture will collapse and the community's social and cultural life will be disrupted. The community is determined to stay and fight for the protection of their land and water. They refuse to accept the losses suffered by other communities and are demanding that their rights, their spring and their way of life be safeguarded.

This photo is for illustrative purposes only.

This case illustrates how the extraction of natural resources can jeopardise the survival, culture and social life of communities. For this community, the manantial is more than just a source of water; it is the centre of their identity, culture and hope. Protecting it is essential if their way of life is to be preserved for future generations.

This photo is for illustrative purposes only.

Other cases

Unfortunately, the previously described harms are not isolated. Across different regions, many indigenous and Afro-descendant peoples face similar pressures when their lands, waters and cultural practices are disrupted by large-scale projects or environmental damage. To demonstrate the extent of these challenges, this toolkit presents two further cases based on publicly available information: the Munduruku people in Brazil and the Línea Negra in the Sierra Nevada de Santa Marta in Colombia. Together, these examples illustrate patterns that are evident in many places, despite each community having its own unique history, identity and relationship with the environment.

Sete Quedas

Some communities from the Kayabi, Munduruku e Apiaká peoples live along the upper Tapajós River and the Teles Pires River, in the Amazon. Over the past decade, large infrastructure projects have altered this region. Four hydroelectric dams have been built or are under construction on the Teles Pires River, a major affluent of the Tapajós River. These projects aim to expand hydropower generation.

This photo is for illustrative purposes only and does not depict Sete Quedas.

One of the main impacts was the destruction and flooding of Sete Quedas, a sacred waterfall on the Teles Pires River. The construction consortium obtained authorisation to dynamite and flood the site in order to build the Teles Pires dam. Beyond its spiritual significance, the area contains the Salto Sete Quedas rapids, which are of great importance in sustaining the traditional way of life of the affected Indigenous peoples. The waterfall serves as a crucial breeding ground for migratory fish that form the primary food source for communities living in the Teles Pires basin. In Munduruku cosmology, Sete Quedas is known as Paribixexe and is considered a place connected to the journey of spirits after death, as well as the dwelling place of the Mother of Fish, Karupi, Karubixexé and the spirits of ancestors.

This photo is for illustrative purposes only and does not depict Sete Quedas.

As stated by the Brazilian National Foundation for the Indigenous People:

“The Teles Pires River is the main socio-cultural axis of the peoples under analysis, and the Sete Quedas Falls are one of the most important symbolic and ecological references for these populations (...). (...) this river, and especially the Sete Quedas, are embedded in the social universe of the indigenous populations and should have been observed as part of the social organisation of these peoples, present as territorial categories of use and occupation, directly associated with intangible and spiritual culture and collective memory, just as they should have been better analysed in the context of assessing the impacts and feasibility of the projects.”

Citation retrieved from TRF-1, AC: 00039474420124013600
0003947-44.2012.4.01.3600, Relator.: Desembargador Federal
Souza Prudente, Data de Julgamento: 30/11/2016, Quinta Turma,
Data de Publicação: 14/03/2017.

This photo is for illustrative purposes only and does not depict Sete Quedas.

Over time, the Sete Quedas have adapted to many external influences, including new technologies and ways of making a living. However, they explain that the destruction of sacred sites threatens their ability to uphold key aspects of their identity and cosmology. Community members often describe the destruction of the Sete Quedas as an irreversible action that continues to affect how they perceive the future of their territory. The Munduruku case illustrates how environmental and infrastructure projects can reshape not only ecosystems, but also cultural and social practices.

Information retrieved from Branford, S. & Torres, M. (2017, 5 January). The end of a People: Amazon dam destroys sacred Munduruku “Heaven”. Mongabay. <https://news.mongabay.com/2017/01/the-end-of-a-people-amazon-dam-destroys-sacred-munduruku-heaven/>.

This photo is for illustrative purposes only and does not depict Sete Quedas.

Línea Negra

The Sierra Nevada de Santa Marta is a mountain range in northern Colombia. It reaches an elevation of around 5,775 metres above sea level and is located approximately 42 kilometres from the Caribbean coast. Spanning the departments of Cesar, Guajira, and Magdalena, the region covers around 17,000 km². The lower elevations are occupied by farming communities, while the mid- and upper-altitude areas are home to the Kogi, Arhuaco, Wiwa and Kankuamo peoples.

Information retrieved from Confederación Indígena Tayrona. (n.d.). Secretos de la Línea Negra de la Sierra Nevada. Confederación Indígena Tayrona. <https://confetayrona.com/secretos-de-la-linea-negra-de-la-sierra-nevada/>.

This photo is for illustrative purposes only.

The Arhuaco, Kogui, Wiwa and Kankuamo peoples of the Sierra Nevada de Santa Marta view their territory as an interconnected network of sacred sites known as the ‘Línea Negra’. Known as Jaba Seshizha, Shetana Zhiwa and Seykutukunumaku, these sites connect land, water and cultural spaces, linking them spiritually and materially to other sacred places. Guided by the principles of Mama Sushi, this interconnected system shapes how the communities care for their land, maintain their traditions, and exercise their ancestral rights.

Information retrieved from Colombia (2018). Decreto 1500 de 2018 – Línea Negra. ACMinería. https://acmineria.com.co/acm/wp-content/uploads/normativas/decreto_1500_de_2018_-_linea_negra.pdf/.

This photo is for illustrative purposes only.

In 2018, the Colombian government issued Decree 1500, recognising the ancestral territory defined by the system of sacred spaces of the Línea Negra. The decree outlines special protections for the territory's cultural, spiritual and environmental dimensions and establishes coordination mechanisms between indigenous authorities and state institutions. It also clarifies that the process of defining boundaries does not affect private property rights, prior consultation procedures, or land-use regulations.

Information retrieved from Colombia, Autor desconocido. (2018). Decreto 1500 de 2018 – Línea Negra. ACMinería. https://acmineria.com.co/acm/wp-content/uploads/normativas/decreto_1500_de_2018_-_linea_negra.pdf/.

This photo is for illustrative purposes only.

Not all sacred sites are currently under the control of Indigenous peoples. Decades of colonisation and internal armed conflict have displaced communities from parts of their territory. Several sites within the Línea Negra are now affected or threatened by mining operations, infrastructure projects and other large-scale developments. The Constitutional Court has previously identified risks to the physical and cultural continuity of several Sierra Nevada peoples, citing repeated violations linked to conflict, displacement and restrictions on collective rights.

Rights

A clear pattern emerges across the four cases presented: human-induced environmental degradation can affect the rights of Afro-descendant and Indigenous peoples in multiple ways. These impacts can take many different forms. For example, they can affect:

land rights

**free, prior
and informed
consent**

**cultural
rights**

land rights

Land rights refer to the recognised relationship between a community and its ancestral or traditionally used territory. These rights include access to the land, the right to use it, the right to control it, and the right to maintain cultural, spiritual, and livelihood practices connected to it.

free, prior and informed consent

Free, prior and informed consent is the right of indigenous peoples and other affected communities to be consulted in a timely, culturally appropriate and meaningful way before any project affecting their lands, resources or ways of life. The consultation must be carried out freely and prior to the start of activities, and be based on full and accessible information.

cultural rights

Cultural rights encompass the ability of individuals and communities to practise, maintain, develop and transmit their cultural expressions, beliefs, traditions and knowledge systems without interference. This includes access to cultural spaces and sacred sites, as well as the environmental conditions necessary for cultural practices to be sustained.

See the **glossary**

Although violations of land rights and free, prior and informed consent (FPIC) tend to be more visible, the impact on cultural rights is often less apparent immediately. For instance, if a community's traditional territory is seized without due process, this constitutes a clear violation of their land rights. Similarly, extractive projects that begin without meaningful consultation or without providing complete information directly breach the community's right to FPIC.

However, consequences for cultural rights, such as the erosion of traditional knowledge, the loss of place-specific ceremonies, or the weakening of community cohesion, may emerge slowly and be more difficult to demonstrate. Nevertheless, highlighting cultural rights violations can provide communities with an additional means of defending their way of life and ensuring its continuity.

It is important to note that cultural rights claims do not replace land rights or FPIC claims. In many situations, land rights and FPIC remain the most direct and suitable legal pathways. Communities should seek legal advice to determine the most appropriate mechanisms for their situation and to understand how cultural rights arguments can complement other strategies.

For more information on these possibilities, please refer to the Case Law Guide and the How to Complain Guide included in this toolkit.

How Can Environmental Degradation Affect Cultural Rights?

As previously mentioned, environmental degradation affects more than just land, water and forests. It also impacts the cultural rights of Afro-descendant and indigenous peoples, affecting their traditions, knowledge, spiritual practices and way of life. The four case studies in this toolkit demonstrate the close link between cultural life and the environment, and how quickly disruption can occur when the environment changes.

When Land Is Taken or Transformed

When land is sold, grabbed, polluted, or transformed by companies, people can lose the spaces where cultural life takes place.

Angelim

In the Angelim Community, the introduction of eucalyptus plantations made it harder to farm, gather forest materials, and live in the way the community always had. As families were pushed out, celebrations, rituals, and shared work declined. The knowledge held by elders weakened as they left or passed away.

There is a cultural loss

When Land Is Taken or Transformed

Linea Negra

In the Linea Negra, many sacred sites that define the spiritual territory of the four Indigenous Peoples are now threatened or blocked by development projects. When a sacred site is damaged or inaccessible, spiritual practices that depend on that place cannot be carried out.

There is a cultural loss

When Water Sources Are Polluted or Disrupted

For many communities, rivers, springs, and wetlands are not only physical resources; they are cultural and spiritual centers.

Cañaverales

In the Cañaverales Community, the agricultural life and festivals related to it are only possible because the land is rich in water resources. If the manantial is polluted, agriculture is impacted, the community might need to leave the land and their festivals, as they are linked to the agriculture and their way of life, could no longer be held.

There is a potential cultural loss

When Water Sources Are Polluted or Disrupted

Angelim

Chemical pollution affected the river where women used to gather, talk, wash clothes. Fishing is no longer possible. Losing this shared space weakened daily interactions and community ties.

**There is change of
their way of life,
therefore,
a cultural loss**

When Displacement Breaks Community Bonds

Angelim

Many members moved to cities after company pressure. Instead of opportunities, many ended up in difficult conditions, including living in *favelas* or facing mental health struggles. With fewer people in the village, festivities disappeared or now happen only once a year.

**There is a
cultural loss**

When Knowledge Cannot Be Transmitted

Angelim

Children now have fewer chances to learn traditional stories, plant diversity, songs, and rituals because the places and activities where knowledge was shared no longer exist.

**There is
a cultural loss**

When Knowledge Cannot Be Transmitted

Munduruku

Environmental destruction caused by illegal mining and deforestation makes it harder to teach young people about fishing places, sacred sites, and forest guardians; knowledge that depends on the land remaining intact.

**There is
a cultural loss**

When Sacred Sites and Spiritual Practices Are Endangered

Spiritual practices often require specific sites, landscapes,
or natural elements.

Linea Negra

Sacred places connected to ancestors and forest spirits are
harmed by development projects, making it difficult to
carry out rituals and spiritual responsibilities.

**There is
a potential
cultural loss**

Across all four situations, we can observe that:

- Cultural rights are deeply connected to the health of lands, waters, forests, and sacred places.
- Environmental degradation disrupts the daily practices that hold communities together, from farming to festivals.
- When displacement occurs, cultural rights are at even greater risk because traditions cannot survive without people practicing them.
- Protecting the environment is also protecting cultural life, identity, and continuity.

At the same time, not every aspect of cultural loss can be formally attributed to a specific actor or legal violation. Some changes occur gradually or through multiple overlapping factors, which can make accountability more complex.

Understanding these connections helps communities and allies identify cultural rights violations and use them as part of a broader strategy to safeguard their ways of life.

The main international instrument that formally recognizes and protects these rights is **ILO Convention 169 on Indigenous and Tribal Peoples**. This convention establishes binding obligations for States that have ratified the convention, to safeguard the land rights, cultural integrity, and participatory decision-making of Indigenous Peoples, including the requirement to guarantee free, prior and informed consultation in decisions affecting their territories.

Importantly, in several countries across Latin America and the Caribbean, ILO Convention 169 has also been interpreted as applicable to **Afro-descendant communities**, reinforcing their collective rights to land, culture, and self-determination in the context of environmental and development projects.

See the **glossary**

biocultural rights

(Sentencia T-622/16)

In line with these international standards, the Colombian Constitutional Court (Sentencia T-622/16) has further advanced the protection of collective rights through the recognition of **biocultural rights**. These rights are grounded in the understanding that people, their cultures, and the natural environment are fundamentally interconnected, and that cultural and biological diversity sustain one another.

See the **glossary**

biocultural rights

(Sentencia T-622/16)

The Court has defined biocultural rights as the rights of **Indigenous and Afro-descendant communities** to manage, protect, and relate to their territories and natural resources according to their own laws, traditions, and customs. This approach acknowledges that for many communities, culture, territory, and nature form an indivisible whole, and that safeguarding ecosystems necessarily involves safeguarding the ways of life, knowledge systems, and cultural practices that have long contributed to their care. By bringing together elements of identity, land, culture, and environmental protection, biocultural rights reinforce the ability of these communities to defend their territories while highlighting their essential role in maintaining biodiversity.

biocultural rights

(Sentencia T-622/16)

The Constitutional Court explains that the international foundation of biocultural rights comes mainly from **ILO Convention 169**, which recognizes the deep connection between the ways of life of Indigenous and tribal peoples and their territories. Article 13 requires States to respect the spiritual and cultural importance these peoples attribute to their lands. The Court has also interpreted several provisions of the Convention as applicable to Afro-descendant communities. Overall, according to the Court, the treaty states the integral link between cultural identity, spiritual worldview, and the biodiversity present in ancestral territories, underpinning the concept of biocultural rights.

biocultural rights

(Sentencia T-622/16)

Another key international instrument mentioned by the Court supporting biocultural rights is the **Convention on Biological Diversity** (1992). According to the Court, this treaty explicitly links biodiversity with the communities that interact with and depend on it, recognizing the essential role that the traditional lifestyles of Indigenous and other ethnic communities play in conserving biological diversity.

biocultural rights

(Sentencia T-622/16)

A third relevant instrument is the **UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples** (2007), which Colombia adopted with clarifications. The declaration recognizes the right of Indigenous Peoples to their cultural identity and affirms that their knowledge, cultures, and traditional practices are essential for sustainable and equitable environmental management. It underscores the need for Indigenous control over their lands, territories, and resources to maintain their institutions and ways of life. While not legally binding, it remains an important interpretive reference. Note that this instrument is only applicable to Indigenous Peoples.

biocultural rights

(Sentencia T-622/16)

Similarly, the **American Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples** (2016) reinforces these principles by recognizing the rights of Indigenous Peoples to self-identification, self-determination, autonomy, cultural integrity, and control over their lands, territories, and resources. This instrument strengthens collective rights across the hemisphere and supports the recognition of related rights, including biocultural rights. Although not legally binding, it serves as a valid interpretive standard for States belonging to the OAS.

biocultural rights

(Sentencia T-622/16)

Finally, the **UNESCO Convention for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage** (2003) is cited. It establishes obligations to protect and safeguard intangible cultural heritage. This includes oral traditions and languages, social and ritual practices, knowledge related to nature and the environment, and traditional artisanal techniques of ethnic communities—all closely linked to biocultural rights. The Convention thus reinforces state responsibilities to preserve and promote the cultural expressions and knowledge systems that sustain the relationship between communities and their territories.

bio-socio-cultural approach

Building on these ideas, a **bio-socio-cultural approach** highlights that the relationship between nature and culture can only be fully understood when the social dimension is taken into account. Communities and their social practices play a central role in shaping, interpreting, and maintaining the interactions between people and the environment. Culture, understood as a way of life rooted in shared knowledge, traditions, and collective activities, guides how communities engage with ecosystems and use natural resources.

See the **glossary**

bio-socio-cultural approach

As we observed in the **case of Angelim**, without this social element, the nature-culture link would not exist, as it is the community that observes, gives meaning to, and interacts with its surroundings. From this perspective, biodiversity, cultural diversity, and social life are mutually reinforcing. Without the community, there is a cultural loss.

Protecting Way of Life as Cultural Heritage

One option for defending your traditions is to frame them as cultural heritage. Cultural heritage is commonly divided into three categories: tangible, intangible, and cultural landscapes. In practice, these forms of heritage often overlap. For example, a traditional ritual (intangible) held at a specific river or mountain (tangible or landscape) shows how cultural meaning depends on both the practice and the place.

However, for legal and administrative processes, you will usually need to fit the cultural element you want to protect into one main category.

A Note of Caution

Recognizing sites or practices as cultural heritage can add an important layer of protection, strengthening visibility, legal recognition, and social support.

However, heritage status does not guarantee full or permanent protection. Heritage-listed sites can still face threats, such as land conflicts, development pressures, weak enforcement, or political changes.

Cultural heritage tools therefore work best alongside other strategies, including land rights, environmental protections, and community-led monitoring, rather than as a substitute for them.

Tangible Cultural Heritage

Physical objects, structures, or places that have cultural, historical, or spiritual significance. This includes buildings, sacred sites, artifacts, monuments, and material expressions of a community's history.

Tangible cultural heritage can be protected as local, national heritage (depending on the application of national legislation) or be inscribed in the UNESCO World Heritage List. For the latter, only States can nominate sites and, if inscribed, they are protected by the UNESCO World Heritage Convention.

Tangible Cultural Heritage

The land itself?

Some scholars argue that the lands of Indigenous Peoples should be recognized as tangible cultural heritage, since their territories carry physical and spiritual meaning, contain sacred places, and hold the material traces of their history. However, this type of recognition is not yet feasible in most legal systems. Existing heritage procedures often focus on specific sites or objects, not entire territories. Because of this, communities usually need to identify concrete elements, such as sacred sites, ceremonial spaces, or traditional structures, when seeking protection under the tangible heritage category.

See Ciocchetti de Souza, M., & Katurchi Exner, C. (2024). A terra indígena como patrimônio cultural brasileiro. *Revista Jurídica da Escola Superior do Ministério Público de São Paulo*, 24, 160–180. Retrieved from https://es.mpsp.mp.br/revista_esmp/index.php/RJESMPSP/article/view/541

Intangible Cultural Heritage

Practices, expressions, knowledge, and skills passed from generation to generation. This includes oral traditions, music, dance, rituals, craftsmanship, agricultural techniques, and social practices.

States can recognize practices, expressions, or skills as cultural heritage, providing measures to support their transmission and safeguard their practice, in the framework of their national legislation. Moreover, States can nominate elements for the Representative or Urgent Safeguarding Lists. Once inscribed, these elements are recognized under the UNESCO Convention for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage.

Intangible Cultural Heritage

Ancestral System of Knowledge of the Arhuaco, Kankuamo, Kogui and Wiwa peoples (Colombia)

As an example, UNESCO has already recognized practices of this kind. In 2022, the Ancestral System of Knowledge of the Arhuaco, Kankuamo, Kogui and Wiwa peoples of the Sierra Nevada de Santa Marta was inscribed on the UNESCO Representative List of the Intangible Cultural Heritage.

This system is made up of sacred mandates that guide how these peoples live in balance with both the physical and spiritual world. Practices include caring for sacred sites, performing rituals such as baptisms and marriage rites, and maintaining traditional dances, songs, and offerings.

The system is transmitted through daily cultural practice, the use of Indigenous languages, teachings about relationships with nature, and participation in community activities. This example shows how knowledge, spirituality, and everyday practices can be recognized as intangible cultural heritage.

Information retrieved from UNESCO. (2022). Ancestral system of knowledge of the four indigenous peoples, Arhuaco, Kankuamo, Kogui and Wiwa of the Sierra Nevada de Santa Marta. Representative List of the Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity. <https://ich.unesco.org/>

Cultural Landscape

Areas where the interaction between people and the environment has produced a space with shared cultural meaning. This can include sacred natural areas, traditional agricultural systems, or territories shaped through long-term cultural use.

Some states recognize cultural landscapes as heritage, but this is a relatively recent category and many countries have not yet implemented specific protection measures.

Cultural landscapes can be nominated for inscription on the World Heritage List. Once inscribed, they are recognized under the UNESCO Convention as heritage sites that reflect the combined natural and cultural value of the area, with guidelines for their safeguarding and management.

Cultural Landscape

Sagihengu and Kamukuwaká (Brazil)

In 2021, the sacred sites Sagihengu and Kamukuwaká, belonging to the Indigenous Peoples of the Upper Xingu (Mato Grosso), were officially recognized as Cultural Heritage of Brazil by IPHAN.

The Waurá, Kalapalo, and Kamayurá peoples requested this protection to ensure continued access to the sites and to safeguard the cultural and spiritual practices linked to them. Both places are essential to the Kwarup, a major interethnic ritual shared by nine Indigenous groups of the Upper Xingu.

Although these groups are distinct, they share myths, ceremonies, exchanges, and a strong sense of collective identity. The Kwarup, held at the end of the dry season, honors deceased leaders through singing, dancing, weeping, traditional music, and communal gatherings.

The heritage listing followed years of collaborative research involving Indigenous communities and national experts. This case demonstrates how cultural heritage mechanisms can protect cultural landscapes where environment, ritual, identity, and ancestral narratives are inseparable.

Traditional Agricultural System

A Traditional Agricultural System is a way of cultivating the land that is developed, practiced, and transmitted by a community over generations. It includes not only farming techniques but also the knowledge, values, and social relationships that guide how people plant, harvest, manage the soil, protect biodiversity, prepare food, and relate to their territory.

These systems are usually adapted to local environments and follow ecological cycles, which means they often help conserve forests, water sources, seeds, and wildlife. Traditional Agricultural Systems are cultural practices as much as they are agricultural ones, shaped by memory, identity, spirituality, and community cooperation.

Because they integrate culture, territory, and sustainable use of the land, Traditional Agricultural Systems can be recognized and protected as part of a community's cultural heritage.

Traditional Agricultural System

Quilombola Communities of the Vale do Ribeira (Brazil)

The Traditional Agricultural System (SAT) of the Quilombola communities in the Vale do Ribeira is a set of knowledge and practices that guide how communities plant, manage the forest, prepare food, and cooperate with each other. Its core is the roça de coivara, a rotational farming method that uses controlled fire to open small fields, which are later left to regenerate. This system follows the rhythms of the forest and supports environmental balance.

Families cultivate a large variety of plants, notably cassava, corn, beans, fruits, and medicinal herbs, using mostly creole seeds that are selected, preserved, and exchanged within the community. The SAT also includes collective work practices like mutirões, shared meals, music, and celebrations, showing how farming, social life, and cultural expression are deeply connected.

Beyond planting, the system encompasses traditional food processing, craftmaking with forest materials, and knowledge related to healing and spirituality. These practices reflect the communities' long history of resistance, their connection to the land, and their cultural continuity.

Information retrieved from IPHAN (2018). Sistema agrícola de comunidades Quilombolas do Vale do Ribeira. BCR – IPHAN. <https://bcr.iphan.gov.br/bens-culturais/sistema-agricola-de-comunidades-quilombolas-do-vale-do-ribeira/>

MOTHER EARTH MSCA POSTDOCTORAL FELLOWSHIP

